

KOSTANECKI-ROBINSON REACTION. PART II. PROPIONYLATION AND BUTYRYLATION OF ORCACETOPHENONE AND ITS MONOMETHYL ETHER.

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In continuation of the work described in Part I orcacetophenone has been propionylated and butyrylated. The condensation products on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid give 7-hydroxy-3 : 5-dimethyl-4-propionomethylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-3-ethyl-4-butyromethyl-5-methylcoumarin respectively. These on treatment with alkali give 7-hydroxy-3 : 4 : 5-trimethylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-3-ethyl-4 : 5-dimethylcoumarin respectively. 7-Hydroxy-2-ethyl-5-methylchromone and 7-hydroxy-2-propyl-5-methylchromone, required for comparison, have been synthesised from the β -diketones obtained by the condensation of orcacetophenone dimethyl ether with ethyl propionate and ethyl butyrate respectively.

Resacetophenone on Kostanecki acetylation gives a chromone (Kostanecki and Rozycki, *Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 102). A similar acetylation of orcacetophenone and its monomethyl ether gave 7-acetoxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin and 7-methoxy-4-acetomethyl-5-methylcoumarin respectively. These on deacetylation gave 7-hydroxy-4 : 5-dimethylcoumarin and 7-methoxy-4 : 5-dimethylcoumarin respectively, as described in the previous part (Sethna and Shah, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **17**, 239). The formation of the 4-substituted *C*-acylcoumarins in Kostanecki acetylation has been observed for the first time in the above work. In view of these interesting results the work has been extended to the propionylation and butyrylation of orcacetophenone and its monomethyl ether.

Orcacetophenone on heating with sodium propionate and propionic anhydride yields a brown viscous mass which cannot be either distilled or crystallised and so is directly treated with concentrated sulphuric acid for the hydrolysis of the *O*-propionyl group, when a product $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ (A) is obtained which gives the acetyl derivative, methyl ether and 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. The product (A) on treatment with alkali gives (B) $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$, which is found to be not identical on direct comparison with 7-hydroxy-2-ethyl-5-methylchromone (III, $R=C_2H_5$) synthesised for the purpose. The structure of 7-hydroxy-3 : 4 : 5-trimethylcoumarin (I, $R=H$) has, therefore, been assigned to (B). The molecular formula of (A) differs from (B) by C_3H_4O which suggests the presence of a propionyl group. This group must be in the pyrone ring as it is easily split off by alkali and also because the product (A) does not give a ferric chloride colouration. The

structure of 7-hydroxy-3:5-dimethyl-4-propionomethylcoumarin (I, R = COC_2H_5) has been, therefore, assigned to (A) by analogy with the results obtained in the acetylation of oracetophenone.

The monomethyl ether of oracetophenone gives on similar propionylation 7-methoxy-3:5-dimethyl-4-propionomethylcoumarin, identical with the methyl ether of (I, R = COC_2H_5).

An attempt has been made in this connection to synthesise 7-hydroxy-3:4:5-trimethylcoumarin through the Pechmann condensation of *p*-orsellinic acid with ethyl α -methyl-acetoacetate. It has, however, been found that under the usual conditions of the reaction neither *p*-orsellinic acid nor methyl *p*-orsellinate condenses with ethyl α -methyl-acetoacetate. Under more drastic conditions, a very small quantity of an acid is obtained which is found to be the same as the acid obtained on heating *p*-orsellinic acid alone with concentrated sulphuric acid under the above conditions of reaction. The acid is probably obtained by the condensation of two molecules of *p*-orsellinic acid and may have the structure (IV, R = COOH) of a diphenyl methyloid derivative, the product obtained on decarboxylation having the structure (IV, R = H).

Oracetophenone on butyrylation gives a brown viscous product which cannot be purified and so is treated directly with concentrated sulphuric acid, when a product is obtained which is supposed to be 7-hydroxy-3-ethyl-4-butyromethyl-5-methylcoumarin (II, R = COC_3H_7) by analogy with the previous work. This on treatment with alkali gives 7-hydroxy-3-ethyl-4:5-dimethylcoumarin (II, R = H), which is found to be not identical on direct comparison with 7-hydroxy-2-propyl-5-methylchromone (III, R = C_3H_7).

The monomethyl ether of oracetophenone on butyrylation gives brown viscous product which can neither be distilled nor crystallised.

Propionylation and butyrylation of monoethyl ether of resacetophenone gives a mixture of chromones and coumarins, the yield of the latter being greater than that of the former (Heilbron, Hey and Lythgoe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1581; 1936, 297). In the propionylation and butyrylation of oracetophenone we have not been able to isolate any chromones. As in the acetylation of oracetophenone, 4-substituted *C*-acylcoumarins have been obtained. The 6-methyl group in oracetophenone, therefore, seems to have a profound influence on the course of the Kostanecki reaction and the effect of this group may be steric.

The chromones required in this work for comparison have been prepared by the condensation of oracetophenone dimethyl ether with ethyl propionate and ethyl butyrate respectively. The β -diketones are treated

with cold hydrobromic acid solution when methoxy chromones are obtained. These on heating with hydriodic acid give 7-hydroxy-2-ethyl-5-methylchromone (III, $R = C_2H_5$) and 7-hydroxy-2-propyl-5-methylchromone (III, $R = C_3H_7$) respectively.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Propionylation of Orcacetophenone: 7-Hydroxy-3:5-dimethyl-4-propionomethylcoumarin (I, $R = COC_2H_5$).—Orcacetophenone (10 g.), prepared by Hoesch's method (*Ber.*, 1915, 48, 1127) was refluxed with sodium propionate (30 g.) and propionic anhydride (100 c.c.) in an oil-bath at 180–190° for 9 hours. The excess of propionic anhydride was distilled over and the reaction mixture added to water. Dark brown viscous oil separated which did not solidify even on keeping for 3 to 4 days in a frigidaire. It was taken up in ether and the ether extract was thoroughly washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The residue from ether extract, a dark brown viscous oil, could not be either distilled at reduced pressure or crystallised and so was treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) and kept for 4 hours. The reaction mixture was then added to ice-cold water, when pale greenish yellow solid separated which was crystallised from rectified spirit in pale yellow tiny silky needles (4.5 g.), m.p. 207.9°. The product gave no fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid or caustic alkalis and showed no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 6.2. $C_{15}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 69.2; H, 6.2 per cent)

The acetyl derivative, prepared as usual with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny shining needles, m.p. 111–113°. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 5.8. $C_{17}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 67.5; H, 6.0 per cent).

7-Methoxy-3:5-dimethyl-4-propionomethylcoumarin, prepared with potassium carbonate and methyl iodide as usual, was crystallised from rectified spirit in faint greenish needles, m.p. 75-77°. (Found: C, 70.1; H, 6.6. $C_{16}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 70.1; H, 6.6 per cent).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from alcohol-acetic acid mixture in yellow needles, m.p. 255-56° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.1. $C_{21}H_{20}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.7 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-3:4:5-trimethylcoumarin (I, R=H).—The product (I, R=COC₂H₅) (3 g.) was shaken up with sodium hydroxide (6%, 40 c.c.) and kept for 3 hours. The reaction mixture was then acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid, when a pasty product came down which solidified on keeping in a frigidaire overnight. It was crystallised from rectified spirit and finally from 50% acetic acid in small slender needles (1 g.), m.p. 195-97°, mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy-2-ethyl-5-methylchromone was depressed by 30°. The product gave bluish fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid and with caustic alkalis. (Found: C, 70.3; H, 6.0. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9 per cent).

The *methyl ether*, prepared as usual by potassium carbonate-methyl iodide method, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in prisms, m.p. 90-92°. (Found: C, 70.7; H, 6.4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C 71.6; H, 6.4 per cent).

Propionylation of Orcacetophenone Monomethyl Ether.—Orcacetophenone monomethyl ether (2 g.), prepared from orcacetophenone, dimethyl sulphate and alkali (Hoesch, *loc. cit.*), was refluxed with sodium propionate (6 g.) and propionic anhydride (20 c.c.) for 8 hours at 180-90°. The brown viscous mass, obtained as residue from ether extract, on working up as above was dissolved in rectified spirit and kept in a frigidaire when tiny faint yellow needles separated (0.4 g.), m.p. 74-76° (mixed m.p. with 7-methoxy-3:5-dimethyl-4-propionomethylcoumarin described above).

(2':4'-Dimethoxy-6'-methyl)-benzoylpropionylmethane.—Dimethyl ether of orcacetophenone (6 g.), prepared from orcacetophenone, dimethyl sulphate and sodium hydroxide (Tambor, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 794) and ethyl propionate (13 g., approximately 4 mol.) were added to pulverised sodium (1.5 g., approx. 2 moi.), the whole being cooled externally by cold water. After the initial vigorous reaction had subsided the reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 115-20° for 1½ hours. On cooling, water was added to decompose the excess of sodium and the mixture was extracted with ether to remove the excess of ethyl propionate and the unreacted dimethyl ether of orcacetophenone.

phenone. The alkaline solution, on acidification with dilute acetic acid, gave an oil. This was taken up in ether, the ether extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and dried. The oil, obtained on evaporation of ether, was distilled under reduced pressure and the fraction which distilled over at $185-90^{\circ}/2-4$ mm. (4 g.) was collected. It gave deep reddish violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 67.2; H, 7.2. $C_{14}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 67.2; H, 7.2 per cent).

7-Methoxy-2-ethyl-5-methylchromone.—The above β -diketone (2 g.) was kept for 24 hours with hydrobromic acid solution (d 1.78, 5 c.c.) and then poured into water. The brown solid, which separated, was treated with dilute sodium hydroxide to remove demethylated chromone if any. The portion insoluble in alkali was crystallised from rectified spirit in long slender needles (0.7 g.), m.p. $130-32^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 71.3; H, 6.3. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.6; H, 6.4 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-2-ethyl-5-methylchromone (III, $R=C_2H_5$).—The above methyl ether (0.3 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) and refluxed in an oil-bath at $130-140^{\circ}$ for 2 hours with hydriodic acid solution (d 1.7, 5 c.c.). The product, obtained on adding the reaction mixture to sodium bisulphite solution, was treated with sodium hydroxide. The portion soluble in alkali came down on acidification with hydrochloric acid and was crystallised from rectified spirit in slender shining needles (0.15 g.), m.p. $195-97^{\circ}$. It gives blue fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 70.3; H, 5.9. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.6, H, 5.9 per cent).

Attempted Pechmann Condensation of Methyl p-Orsellinate and p-Orsellinic Acid with Ethyl α -Methylacetoacetate.

(i) Methyl *p*-orsellinate (1 g.), prepared from *p*-orsellinic acid and diazomethane (Herzig, *Monatsh*, 1903, 24, 894), ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (1 g.) and sulphuric acid (80%, 10 c.c.) were kept for 40 hours. On working up as usual the product was found to be only *p*-orsellinic acid.

(ii) *p*-Orsellinic acid (5 g.), ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (4.5 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) were kept overnight and next day the reaction mixture was heated at $60-70^{\circ}$ for 4 hours. *p*-Orsellinic acid was obtained back on working up the reaction mixture as usual.

(iii) The above reaction mixture (ii) was heated on a water-bath at $60-70^{\circ}$ for 16 hours and poured into water. The product obtained was filtered, washed with water and treated with sodium bicarbonate solution when the whole of it went into solution. The product, obtained on acidi-

fication, was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny pale greenish needles (0.3 g.), m.p. 235-37° (efferv.). [Found: C, 63.9; H, 4.7. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ (IV, R=COOH) requires C, 64.0; H, 4.0 per cent). It gave greenish blue colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and intense greenish fluorescence with alkali. The above product was heated for 5 minutes at 240-50° in an oil-bath till the effervescence ceased, when a solid was obtained which was crystallised from alcohol in tiny pale yellow needles, m.p. 265-67°. [Found: C, 70.6; H, 5.5. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ (IV, R=H) requires C, 70.3; H, 4.7 per cent]. The product gave pale bluish green colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and an intense greenish fluorescence with alkali.

Heating p-Orsellinic Acid with Concentrated Sulphuric Acid.—*p*-Orsellinic acid (3 g.) was heated with concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) for 16 hours at 60-70°. The product, obtained on adding the reaction mixture to water, was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny yellow needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 235-37° (efferv.), mixed m.p. with the acid obtained in (iii) above was the same.

Butyrylation of Orcacetophenone: 7-Hydroxy- 3-ethyl- 4-butyromethyl- 5-methylcoumarin (II, R=COC₂H₅).—Orcacetophenone (10 g.), sodium butyrate (30 g.) and butyric anhydride (100 c.c.) were refluxed in an oil-bath at 180-90° for 8 hours, and the reaction mixture was added to water. Excess of sodium bicarbonate solution was added and the whole kept in a frigidaire. The brown viscous oil, which separated, did not solidify and so was taken up in ether. The ether extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. The brown viscous oil, obtained from the ether extract, could neither be distilled nor crystallised out and hence was directly treated with concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) and kept for about 2 hours. The yellowish solid, obtained on pouring the reaction mixture into cold water, was crystallised from rectified spirit (charcoal) in pale yellow silky needles (6 g.), m.p. 155-56°. (Found: C, 70.6; H, 6.8. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 70.8; H, 6.9 per cent).

The product gave no fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid or with caustic alkalis and gave no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 79-80°. (Found: C, 69.2; H, 6.7. $C_{19}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 69.1; H, 6.7 per cent).

The *methyl ether*, prepared as usual by the potassium carbonate-methyl iodide method, was crystallised from alcohol in tiny yellow needles, m.p.

51-54°. (Found: C, 71.4; H, 7.4. $C_{18}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 71.5; H, 7.3 per cent).

The 2:4-*dinitrophenylhydrazone*, prepared as usual, was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny yellow needles, m.p. 253-54° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.5. $C_{23}H_{24}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.0 per cent).

7-*Hydroxy-3-ethyl-4:5-dimethylcoumarin* (II, R=H).—The condensation product (II, R=COC₂H₅) was treated with sodium hydroxide (10% 40 c.c.) and kept for 3 hours. The product, obtained on acidification, was crystallised from rectified spirit in clusters of white tiny needles (2 g.), m.p. 170-72°. Mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy-2-propyl-5-methylchromone was depressed by 30°. (Found: C, 71.4; H, 6.4. $C_{18}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.6; H, 6.4 per cent). The product gave bluish fluorescence with concentrated sulphuric acid and caustic alkalis.

The *methyl ether*, prepared by the potassium carbonate-methyl iodide method, was crystallised from rectified spirit in colourless rectangular prisms, m.p. 79-81°. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 7.1. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 72.4; H, 6.9 per cent).

Attempted Butyrylation of Orcacetophenone Monomethyl Ether.

Orcacetophenone monomethyl ether (2 g.), sodium butyrate (6 g.) and butyric anhydride (20 c.c.) were refluxed for 8 hours at 180-90°. The reaction mixture on working up as before gave thick brown oil which charred on an attempt at distillation. It did not give any crystals on treatment with various solvents.

(2':4'-*Dimethoxy-6'-methyl*)-*benzoyl-butrylmethane*.—Orcacetophenone dimethyl ether (6 g.) and ethyl butyrate (13 g., approx. 4 mols.) were added to pulverised sodium (1.5 g., approx. 2 mols.). After the initial vigorous reaction had subsided the reaction mixture was heated in an oil-bath at 115-20° for 1½ hours. On working up as before, a brownish oil was obtained which distilled at 220-25°/20-25 mm. to a pale yellow oil (4 g.). It gave deep reddish violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 68.9; H, 7.9. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 68.2; H, 7.6 per cent).

The *copper salt*, prepared from the above β -diketone and copper acetate, was crystallised from benzene in dark bluish green needles, m.p. 175-77°. [Found: Cu, 11.1. $(C_{18}H_{18}O_4)_2$ Cu requires Cu, 10.8 per cent].

7-*Methoxy-2-propyl-5-methylchromone*.—The above β -diketone (2 g.) was kept for 40 hours with hydrobromic acid solution (d 1.78, 7 c.c.) and

then poured into water. The product obtained was treated with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. This, however, gave nothing on acidification. The alkali-insoluble portion, after thorough washing with water, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in rectangular prisms (0.8 g.), m.p. $9-9.8^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 6.9. $C_{14}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 72.4; H, 6.9 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-2-propyl-5-methylchromone (III, $R=C_3H_7$)—The above methyl ether (0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (3 c.c.) and refluxed with hydriodic acid solution (*d* 1.7, 3 c.c.) for 1 hour in an oil-bath at $145-55^{\circ}$. The product, obtained on pouring the reaction mixture into sodium bisulphite solution, was treated with dilute sodium hydroxide solution. The portion, insoluble in alkali, was found to be the undemethylated methyl ether. The product, obtained on acidification of the alkaline solution with hydrochloric acid, on crystallisation from rectified spirit gave needles, m.p. $163-65^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 6.5. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.6; H, 6.4 per cent).

All the analyses recorded are microanalyses. Further work on the Kostanecki-Robinson reaction on various *o*-hydroxy-ketones is in progress.